

MATHEMATICS REFORM IN POST-PRIMARY SCHOOLS IN IRELAND: OPINIONS OF PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS

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INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

As part of the OECD Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) 2012 programme in Ireland, a survey of in-service post-primary mathematics teachers was undertaken, with full results reported by Cosgrove, Perkins, Shiel, Fish & McGuinness (2012). One of the main aims of this questionnaire was to obtain opinions and feedback about the implementation of Project Maths from a nationally representative sample of teachers. In 2015, we gave a subset of this survey to a group of pre-service mathematics teachers immediately before and after a four-month teaching placement. A more complete and detailed description of this project and its outcomes can be found in Ní Fhloinn, Nolan, Hoehne Candido & Guerrero (2018). We also added eight original questions to the survey, and we briefly consider some of the responses in this short paper. A detailed discussion of these is beyond the scope of this short paper, but we have chosen to focus on three questions that yielded some interesting results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The respondents in this survey were in their third year in university, meaning that they sat their Leaving Certificate in June 2012 at the latest, and so had experienced at most two of the five strands of Project Maths, introduced during their final two years at school, as it was implemented on a phased basis. Therefore, we asked respondents about the difference between their own school experience and that of the Project Maths approach, as well as whether the Project Maths approach agrees well with what content they thought should be taught and how they thought it should be taught. The results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Pre-service teachers’ responses to survey statements (n=25 for Pre and n=19 for Post)

	Pre/post placement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
There is a clear distinction between the type of mathematics teaching that I experienced in secondary school and the Project Maths approach	Pre	56%	36%	8%	0%
	Post	26%	47%	16%	11%
The Project Maths approach agrees well with my views on <u>what</u> mathematics content should be taught	Pre	8.7%	82.6%	4.3%	4.3%
	Post	0%	79%	21%	0%
The Project Maths approach agrees well with my views on <u>how</u> mathematics should be taught	Pre	12.5%	83.3%	4.2%	0%
	Post	21%	58%	21%	0%

It can be seen that in relation to the question about there being a clear distinction between their own experience in school and the Project Maths approach, only 8% of pre-placement students disagreed, whereas post-placement, this had increased to 27%. This echoes the findings of Jeffes, Jones, Wilson, Lamont, Straw, Wheeler & Dawson (2013), who found that “*there does not appear to have been a substantial shift in what teachers are asking students to do ... traditional approaches to mathematics teaching and learning continue to be widespread*” (p. 4). Similarly, for the question regarding content, 91.3% of pre-placement respondents agreed or strongly agreed with the Project Maths approach, compared to 79% post-placement. For how this content should be taught, 95.8% agreed or strongly agreed pre-placement, which also dropped to 79% afterwards.

Respondents were asked to comment further for the latter two questions, and a thematic analysis of these open-ended responses was conducted. In relation to Project Maths agreeing with their view of *what* content should be taught, the strongest themes emerging pre-placement were “real-life applications”, “better understanding”, “better for university”, and “easier”; whereas post-placement, the first three of these themes still emerged strongly, but “easier” was no longer mentioned, replaced by “topics omitted” and “no real difference”. For the question regarding *how* the content was taught, the strongest themes pre-placement were “real-life applications”, “better understanding”, “too wordy”, and “still need to teach skills”; while post-placement, the first two themes were still prominent, but others such as “bad for weaker students”, “more problem-solving” and “time pressure” also emerged.

The sample size in question was small and only thirteen students completed both the pre- and post-surveys, meaning that statistical testing would not be reliable; however, the pre-service teachers’ responses, combined with those reported in Ní Fhloinn et al (2018), provide an insight into the opinions of teachers who had the experience of being trained during the transitional period in which Project Maths was being introduced on a phased basis into schools.

REFERENCES

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